

Derivatives of paniculatin and their antifungal activity[†]

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The antifungal activity of the derivatives of paniculatin (1), i.e. paniculol (2), ester derivatives of paniculatin [3(a-f)], 3-hydroxy paniculol (4), 1,2,20,21,22,23-hexahydro paniculatin (5a), 6 α ,7 α -dihydroxy-1,2,20,21,22,23-hexahydropaniculatin (5b), 2-aminothiazolo[4,5-d][1,2,20,21,22,23-hexahydro]paniculatin (6a), 2-aminothiazolo[4,5-d][6 α ,7 α -dihydroxy-1,2,20,21,22,23-hexahydro]paniculatin (6b), isopropylidene derivative of 2 (7) are discussed.

The plants of Meliaceae¹ family are widely distributed in the North-Eastern Region of India. Some species of it are popularly known as Neem, Bandardima, Poma, Gandheli poma², etc. These plants are used in folk medicine as antifeedant and antifungal agents. Phytochemical investigation of Meliaceae family has revealed the occurrence of limonoids (a tetranortriterpenoid), most of them showing antifungal activity. Among the family Meliaceae, the species *Chisocheton paniculatus*³ is the most popular, whose powdered fruits show marked antifungal activities. A petroleum ether extract of fruits of *Chisocheton paniculatus* yielded a reported⁴ limonoid^{5,6} paniculatin (1). However no data are available about the biological activity of these compounds and their derivatives. Therefore, we report here the antifungal activity of paniculatin (1) and their derivatives (Fig. 1) and the comparison of their activity.

*Chisocheton paniculatus*⁷ (Fam : Meliaceae) Hiern occurs as a tree in the forests of Assam, the fruit of which is capsule, 1.5–3 inches across, globose with pyriform base. It has been reported that a number of species of this family exhibit physiological activity¹.

In connection with our studies on the Meliaceae of the North-Eastern Region of India we investigated the fruits and heartwood of *Chisocheton paniculatus*, plant from this region. The plant material was collected from tropical evergreen forest of Nambor Reserve Forest of Golaghat district of Assam, India.

Limonoids have attracted much attention because of the marked insect antifeedant and growth regulating, antifungal activity of azadirachtin and related limonoids isolated from the neem tree and also of few limonoids isolated from

the fruits of *Chisocheton paniculatus* Hiern^{3,8–9}. We report here the isolation and identification of paniculol (2), and chemical transformations of 1 and 2 to new limonoids and their antifungal activities.

Petroleum ether extract of powdered heart-wood of *Chisocheton paniculatus* yielded a complex mixture of gummy material. After careful chromatographic separation one compound was isolated (TLC) and on crystallization (benzene : MeOH :: 9 : 1) gave pure crystalline white solid (plates) with a m.p. 181°. The compound gave a purple spot on tlc plate when sprayed with vanillin/H₂SO₄ followed by heating at 95°. A positive Libermann-Burchard reaction and yellow coloration with tetranitromethane (TNM) indicated that the compound is an unsaturated triterpene. The pure compound was identified as paniculol (2) by comparison of their m.p., IR and ¹H NMR data with the reported values⁴, as well as by comparing with authentic samples. In the ¹H NMR spectrum of 1, the two protons geminal to the acetoxy groups appearing at δ 5.42 and 5.47 in its diacetate compound, shifted and appeared as multiplet centered at δ 4.30.

Mild alkaline hydrolysis of 1 with methanolic KOH gave the corresponding diol (2), C₂₆H₃₄O₄, m.p. 181°. In the ¹H NMR spectrum of 2 the 2 protons geminal to the acetoxy groups appearing at δ 5.42 and 5.47 in 1 shifted and appeared as multiplet centered at δ 4.30.

On acetylation of acid (aliphatic/aromatic) with SOCl₂/PCl₅ gave the acid chloride. This acid chloride on treatment with the compound 2 gave corresponding esters 3e-f. All the acid chlorides used were prepared using the known method¹⁰.

[†]Dedicated to Professor S. M. Mukherji.

Aliphatic esters : R = ethanoate (3a), propanoate (3b), butanoate (3c); Aromatic esters : R = benzoate (3d), phenyl acetate (3e), *p*-nitrobenzoate (3f)

Fig. 1. Reaction scheme

On hydrogenation of paniculatin (**1**) in presence of palladium/calcium carbonate gave the hydrogenated product **5a** and characterized as 1,2,20,21,22,23-hexahydropaniculatin, C₃₀H₄₄O₆, m.p. 213°. In ¹H NMR spectrum, the appearance of new peaks at δ 2.06, 2.61, 2.80, 4.14, 4.18 suggest the saturated carbon and disappearance of unsaturated carbon protons peak at δ 6.39, 6.62, 6.80 and 7.53.

On mild alkaline hydrolysis of **5a** with methanolic KOH gave the corresponding diol **5b**, C₂₆H₄₀O₄, m.p. 95° and characterized as 6 α ,7 α -dihydroxy-1,2,20,21,22,23-hexahydropaniculatin.

On treatment of **5a** with thiourea in presence of chlorine gas gave the heterocyclic compound **6a** (2-aminothiazolo [4,5-*d*][1,2,20,21,22,23-hexahydro]paniculatin), C₃₁H₄₄O₅N₂S, m.p. 88°. In the ¹H NMR spectrum a singlet is seen at δ 6.43 for -NH₂ protons.

Again, treatment of **5b** with thiourea in presence of chlorine gas gave the heterocyclic compound **6b** (2-aminothiazolo[4,5-*d*][6 α ,7 α -dihydroxy-1,2,20,21,22,23-hexahydro]paniculatin), C₃₁H₄₄O₅N₂S, m.p. 88°. In the ¹H

NMR spectrum singlet is seen at δ 6.43 for -NH₂ protons.

Treatment of the diol **2** with acetone in the presence of catalytic amount of sulphuric acid at room temperature gave the corresponding isopropylidene derivative **7**, C₂₉H₃₈O₄, m.p. 69°.

Results and discussion

Antifungal activities of the above compounds have been shown against two different fungi *Drechslera oryzae* and *Rhizoctonia solani* using methanol as solvent by Inhibition Zone Technique⁸. Table 1 shows the results of antifungal tests for different compounds. Experiment was observed for 10 days.

From the Table 1 it is seen that the compound **1** (non hydrogenated) has higher activity than its corresponding hydrogenated product **5a** and similarly compound **2** has better activity than its corresponding hydrogenated product **5b**. Thus we can say that the lowering of activities of both **5a** and **5b** is due to the participation of six hydrogen atoms in 1, 2, 20, 21, 22 and 23 positions. In other words

Table 1. Antifungal activities (inhibition zone technique) (inhibition in %) F₁ = *Rhizoctonia solani*, F₂ = *Drechslera oryzae*, host of the fungi = rice

Sl. no.	No. of days	Sample no.	Concentration (100%)	
			F ₁	F ₂
i	10	1	73.75	75.90
ii	10	2	84.31	85.00
iii	10	3a	72.31	76.35
iv	10	3b	73.34	77.37
v	10	3c	72.31	73.65
vi	10	3d	68.37	68.81
vii	10	3e	65.49	66.24
viii	10	3f	63.33	64.52
ix	10	4	94.21	94.82
x	10	5a	60.21	62.54
xi	10	5b	66.10	68.21
xii	10	6a	93.98	94.65
xiii	10	6b	67.42	69.42
xiv	10	7	93.75	93.88

the α,β -unsaturated carbonyl group and the furan ring enhance the activities of the compounds **1** and **2**. Again we see that the compound **4** has more activity than **2** which in turn more active than **1**. In this case probably more activity of **2** in comparison to **1** is observed due to the two hydroxyl groups at 6 and 7 positions in the former compound. Similarly the maximum activity of the compound **4** is due to the three hydroxyl groups at 3, 6 and 7 positions. Thus greater the number of hydroxyl groups more will be the antifungal activities of the compounds. Maximum activity of the compound **6** is due to the presence of the sulphur atom in the compound. Similarly the acetone moiety (isopropylidene derivative) enhances the higher activity of the compound **7**. Again aromatic esters **3d-f** have better antifungal activity than the aliphatic esters **3a-c**.

Experimental

General procedures : Melting points were determined in open capillaries on a Mettler air heated (Model FP 62) apparatus and are uncorrected. Optical rotations were taken on a optical activity polarimeter (Model AA1000). UV spectra were recorded in MeOH on a Hitachi 320 and Jasco UV-Vis 7800 spectrophotometers; IR, on a Perkin-Elmer system 2000 FT IR spectrometer (ν_{\max} in cm^{-1}), and NMR spectra on a Varian EM-360 L NMR spectrometer using TMS as internal reference (chemical shifts in δ ppm). Mass spectra were recorded on LC-MS, Bruker (Model esquire 3000) mass spectrometer. Thin layer chromatography (TLC) and preparative TLC were performed on silica gel-G (E.

Merck) and column chromatography were on silica gel (B.D.H.) of 60–120 mesh size.

Plant material : The fruits and heartwood of *Chisocheton paniculatus* Hiern were collected from Nambor Reserve Forest of Golaghat, Assam, India during May 2000. Identification was made by Dr. S. C. Nath, Scientist, Regional Research Laboratory, Jorhat from the Herbarium species maintained in the Institute.

Extraction and isolation : Collected fruits of *Chisocheton paniculatus* were first shed dried and grind. 500 g of powdered fruits were extracted with (60–80°) petroleum ether in a soxhlet apparatus. The extract on concentration under reduced pressure gave 15 g of light yellow material. These materials were washed several times by petroleum ether followed by ethanol. After careful chromatographic separation one compound was isolated and on crystallization (benzene : MeOH :: 9 : 1) gave pure crystalline solid (plates) compound.

Paniculatin (**1**), the reported limonoid was isolated from the oil obtained after trituration of the gummy material with pet. ether, as a pure compound (preparative TLC, TLC, column chromatography) and identified by comparing with an authentic sample (TLC, IR, m.m.p.).

Paniculatin (1) : Crystalline solid (MeOH); m.p. 192° (lit.⁴, m.p. 186–188°) $[\alpha]_{\text{D}}^{25} +118^{\circ}$ (c 0.5), (lit.⁶ $[\alpha]_{\text{D}}^{25} +119^{\circ}$ (c 0.5); UV λ_{\max} 220 nm (ϵ 10000); IR ν_{\max} 1750, 1675, 1505 and 875 cm^{-1} ; EIMS (70 eV) $[M^+]$ 494, calcd. for $\text{C}_{30}\text{H}_{38}\text{O}_6$.

Extraction and isolation of paniculatol :

Collected heartwood of *Chisocheton paniculatus* were first shed dried and grind. 500 g of powdered heartwood material were extracted with (60–80°) petroleum ether in a soxhlet apparatus. The extract on concentration under reduced pressure gave 12.5 g of light yellow material. These materials were washed several times by petroleum ether followed by ethanol. After careful chromatographic separation one compound was isolated and crystallization (benzene : MeOH :: 9 : 1) gave pure crystalline white solid (plates) compound.

Paniculatol (2) : Crystalline solid (MeOH); m.p. 181° (lit.⁴, m.p. 180–82°); $[\alpha]_{\text{D}}^{25} +21.5$ (c 0.67, CHCl_3) (lit.⁶ $[\alpha]_{\text{D}}^{25} +22.5$ (c 0.67, CHCl_3); UV λ_{\max} 220 nm (ϵ 117000); IR ν_{\max} 3400, 1675, 1500 and 875 cm^{-1} ; EIMS (70 eV) $[M^+]$ 410, calcd. for $\text{C}_{26}\text{H}_{34}\text{O}_4$.

Compound 2 : Paniculatin (**1**) (1.01 mmol, 0.5 g) was left at room temperature for 12 h in methanolic KOH (5%, 25 ml) then it was refluxed for 2 h in a water bath. Usual work up gave the corresponding diol (**5**) which was crystal-

lized, m.p. 181°, from methanol.

Compound 3a : Compound **2** (1 mmol) was placed in a 250 ml two-necked flask and dissolved in acetone (dry) (50 ml) provided with a reflux condenser and dropping funnel. Into the flask containing the alcohol and cooled in ice, acetyl chloride (2 mmol) was added dropwise under CaCl₂ guard. It was then refluxed for 2 h and allowed to stand for half an hour. The reaction mixture was poured into water, washed with a little NaHCO₃ solution, then with water, and dried with anhydrous Na₂SO₄ and extracted with dichloromethane as usual procedure. The yield was 92% (0.456 g), m.p. 192°.

Compounds **3b-f** were prepared using the above procedure. All the physical and spectroscopic data are given in Table 2.

Compound 4 : Dihydroxy compound of **1** (**2**) (250 mmol, 102.5 g) was dissolved in 50 ml dried methanol. Solution was cooled in ice bath. Now excess amount of sodium borohydride was added gradually under stirring condition until effervescences was ceased.

After completion of the reaction (TLC), solvent was evaporated completely and worked up by usual procedure. The product (white crystal) was recrystallized in alcohol (m.p. 157°), yield 98%.

Compound 5a : 6 α -Acetoxy azadirone (**1**) (paniculatin) (2.02 mmol, 1 g) in methanol (40 ml) was stirred with palladium/calcium carbonate (0.5 g) under an atmosphere of hydrogen for 6 h in a PAR hydrogenation apparatus. The mixture was filtered, removal of solvent under reduced pressure gave 1,2,20,21,22,23-hexahydro paniculatin (**5a**), which was crystallized from methanol, m.p. 213°. The spectral data are given in the Table 2.

Compound 5b : 1,2,20,21,22,23-Hexahydro paniculatin (**5a**) (1 mmol, 0.5 g) was left at room temperature for 12 h in methanolic KOH (5%, 25 ml) then it was refluxed for 2 h in a water bath. On usual work up gave a corresponding diol 6 α ,7 α -dihydroxy-1,2,20,21,22,23-hexahydro-paniculatin (**5b**), which was crystallized from methanol, m.p. 95°.

Compound 6a : A mixture of (**5a**) (2 mmol, 1 g) and thiourea (10 mmol, 0.15 g) was taken in a two necked 250 ml r.b. flask fitted with a reflux condenser provided with a calcium chloride guard tube. Chlorine gas was passed through the solution. The reaction mixture was warmed slightly in a water bath. A sudden exothermic reaction occurs and all the thiourea passes into solution. The resulting solution was refluxed for 30 min and then cooled in an ice bath and then extracted with a suitable solvent. Recrystallized from 2 N HCl solution. The spectral data are given in

Proposed mechanism for the formation of compound 6

the Table 2.

Compound 6b : A mixture of (**5b**) (0.5 mmol, 0.25 g) and thiourea (10 mmol, 0.15 g) was taken in a two necked 250 ml r.b. flask fitted with a reflux condenser provided with a calcium chloride guard tube. Chlorine gas was passed through the solution. The reaction mixture was warmed slightly in a water bath. A sudden exothermic reaction occurred and all the thiourea passes into solution. The resulting solution was refluxed for 30 min and then cooled in an ice bath and then extracted with a suitable solvent. Recrystallized from 2 N HCl solution. The spectral data are given in the Table 2.

Isopropylidene derivative 7 : The diol (**2**) (0.24 mmol, 0.0984 g) was kept at room temperature in dry acetone (20 ml) with two drops concentrated H₂SO₄. The reaction mixture was stirred and followed by tlc. Within 2 h the reaction was completed. Excess acetone was removed under reduced pressure. The residue was diluted with water and product extracted with ether. On removal of ether under reduced pressure gave the isopropylidene derivative (**7**). Crystallization of the product from methanol gave pure compound, C₂₉H₄₄O₄, m.p. 69°. The physical and spectroscopic data are given in Table 2.

Inhibition zone technique⁸ :

(A) *Preparation of assay plates* : Potato Dextrose Agar (PDA) medium was prepared and sterilized as usual. Flat bottom, 90 mm pyrex petriplates were used. Fifteen (15) ml of sterilized hot (80–90°) agar medium were poured into the bottom of the petriplate. These PDA plates were stored in refrigerator overnight.

(B) *Test fungi* : Cultures of the test fungi were grown on PDA for 7 days at the optimum temperature of 30 ± 1° for growth. The test fungi were : (1) *Rhizoctonia solani*⁹ and (2) *Drechslera oryzae*^{11,12}.

(C) *Test sample* : A 100% pure solution of the test chemi-

Table 2. Physical and spectral data of compound 1-7

Compd. no.	M.p. (°C)	Yield (%)	Molecular weight (g)	Molecular formula	IR (ν_{\max} , cm^{-1})	^1H NMR (δ , ppm)
1	192	3	494	$\text{C}_{30}\text{H}_{38}\text{O}_6$	1742 (C=O), 1669 (C=O), 1503, 872 (β -substituted furan)	1.13 (s, 5CH ₃), 2.16 (6H, s, 2Ac), 6.39 (1H, d, H-1), 6.80 (1H, d, H-2), 4.77 (1H, H-6), 4.77 (1H, H-7), 7.51 and 7.53 (1H, m, furan α -H), 6.62 (1H, m, furan β -H)
2	181	97	410	$\text{C}_{26}\text{H}_{34}\text{O}_4$	3443 (OH), 1662 (C=O), 1501, 873 (β -substituted furan)	3.90 (2H, s, OH)
3a	192	93	494	$\text{C}_{30}\text{H}_{38}\text{O}_6$	1742 (C=O), 1669 (C=O), 1503, 872 (β -substituted furan)	1.13 (s, 5CH ₃), 2.16 (6H, s, 2Ac), 6.39 (1H, d, H-1), 6.80 (1H, d, H-2), 4.77 (1H, H-6), 4.77 (1H, H-7), 7.51 and 7.53 (1H, m, furan α -H), 6.62 (1H, m, furan β -H)
3b	Gummy	94	522	$\text{C}_{32}\text{H}_{42}\text{O}_6$	1742 (C=O), 1669 (C=O), 1503, 872 (β -substituted furan)	1.13 (s, 5CH ₃), 1.21 (6H, t, -CH ₃), 2.56 (4H, m, -CH ₂), 6.39 (1H, d, H-1), 6.80 (1H, d, H-2), 4.77 (1H, H-6), 4.77 (1H, H-7), 7.51 and 7.53 (1H, m, furan α -H), 6.62 (1H, m, furan β -H)
3c	Gummy	91	550	$\text{C}_{34}\text{H}_{46}\text{O}_6$	1742 (C=O), 1669 (C=O), 1503, 872 (β -substituted furan)	0.90 (6H, t, -CH ₃), 1.70 (4H, m, -CH ₂), 2.38 (4H, t, -CH ₂)
3d	Gummy	83	578	$\text{C}_{36}\text{H}_{50}\text{O}_6$	1742 (C=O), 1669 (C=O), 1503, 872 (β -substituted furan)	0.90 (6H, t, -CH ₃), 1.37 (4H, m, -CH ₂), 1.61 (4H, m, -CH ₂), 2.32 (4H, t, -CH ₂)
3e	99	98	618	$\text{C}_{40}\text{H}_{42}\text{O}_6$	1742 (C=O), 1669 (C=O), 1503, 872 (β -substituted furan)	7.24–7.99 (10H, m, Ar-H)
3f	Gummy	92	646	$\text{C}_{42}\text{H}_{46}\text{O}_6$	1742 (C=O), 1669 (C=O), 1503, 872 (β -substituted furan)	3.58 (4H, s, -CH ₂), 7.15–7.28 (10H, m, Ar-H)
4	143	97	412	$\text{C}_{26}\text{H}_{36}\text{O}_4$	3446 (OH)	6.39 (1H, d, H-1), 6.80 (1H, d, H-2), 3.90 (2H, s, OH)
5a	213	96	500	$\text{C}_{30}\text{H}_{44}\text{O}_6$	1737 (C=O), 1700 (C=O)	1.13 and 0.87 (s, 5CH ₃), 2.06 (1H, d, H-1), 2.80 (1H, d, H-2), 2.61 (s, H-20), 2.06 (s, H-22), 4.18 (s, H-21), 4.14 (s, H-23)
5b	95	97	416	$\text{C}_{26}\text{H}_{40}\text{O}_4$	1700 (C=O), 3458 (OH)	2.06 (1H, d, H-1), 2.80 (1H, d, H-2), 2.61 (s, H-20), 2.06 (s, H-22), 4.18 (s, H-21), 4.14 (s, H-23), 3.70 (2H, s, OH)
6a	88	89	556	$\text{C}_{31}\text{H}_{44}\text{N}_2\text{O}_5\text{S}$	1741 (C=O)	2.06 (1H, d, H-1), 2.61 (1H, d, H-20), 2.61 (s, H-20), 2.06 (s, H-22), 4.18 (s, H-21), 4.14 (s, H-23), 6.43 (s, NH ₂)
6b	84	88	472	$\text{C}_{27}\text{H}_{40}\text{N}_2\text{O}_3\text{S}$	3427 (OH)	2.06 (1H, d, H-1), 2.61 (s, H-20), 2.06 (s, H-22), 4.18 (s, H-21), 4.14 (s, H-23), 3.70 (2H, s, OH), 6.43 (s, NH ₂)
7	69	85	450	$\text{C}_{29}\text{H}_{38}\text{O}_4$	1670 (C=O), 1512, 875 (β -substituted furan)	3.37 (6H, s, acetamide)

cals were prepared in methanol and acetone. The fungicide (test sample) was thoroughly mixed by stirring before use.

(D) *Setting up the assays* : The PDA plates were taken out from the refrigerator. Five holes with two 2 mm size were made on the media with the help of cork borer and filled up the holes with 0.1 ml of the test fungicide small

disc (0.7 cm) of the fungus culture was cut with a sterile cork borer and transferred aseptically in the center of the petriplate containing the medium. Suitable checks were kept where the culture disch were grown under same condition on PDA without fungicide.

(E) *Incubation* : These petriplates were incubated at 30

$\pm 1^\circ$ and observed for inhibition zone starting from 24 h onwards.

(F) *Estimation of toxicity* : The colony diameter was measured every twenty four hours and compared with check to find out the inhibition zone as a measure of fungitoxicity.

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